

Agenda draft for the Diamond Open Access Expertise Centre Year 2025

Authors: Bregt Lameris, Femke Holwerda, Juliana Costa Pitanguy, Maria E. Constantin

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Feedback received from: Chiara Livio, Susanne van Rijn, Sible Andringa, Jean-Sebastien Caux, Dirk van Gorp

Short summary

The Expertise centre is taking shape by acquiring partners, advisors, and members. For the year 2025, the following results and concrete activities are planned for our four main target groups: editors of Diamond Open Access (OA) journals (including also student journals), researchers (role as authors and reviewers), Institutional Publishers and Service Providers (IPSPs), and librarians. The resources and agenda for policy and funders are not so detailed as the other target groups because we are missing members with such expertise.

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1. Agenda aimed at Diamond OA Journal editors.

The aim of the expertise centre is to support editors in either starting/flipping or professionalizing an existing journal.

Short description	Timeline * Lead	Goal	Comments
Content for openaccess.nl	Q1-Q4 Maria	Launch the expertise centre on openaccess.nl and update website as necessary.	Femke will showcase/develop content for the Editors subpage.
Write relevant content for the target group on social media (LinkedIn)	Q1-Q4 Juliana (Bregt)	Have a consistent presence on LinkedIn. Femke will provide at least one relevant post for journal editors per month.	E.g. “Diamond of the season/ In the spotlight”
Newsletter to be sent to the members of the Expertise Centre	Q1-Q4 Maria (Femke. Bregt)	Newsletter x 4 times/ year (each lead should have a piece for every quarter) 8th of March (M), 27th of June (B), 26th of September (B), 19th of December (F)	Femke will need to provide at least one content piece relevant to journal editors. E.g. “Diamond of the season/ In the spotlight”
Guide to flipping a journal to Diamond OA	Q1 Maria	Via this guide we provide information for editors on how they can transition their journal to a Diamond OA model.	This is a collaboration with the national WGOA, and the resource is useful together with the NWO call .
Make an inventory of resources for professionalizing an existing journal and highlight it on openaccess.nl	Q1 Femke	Simple but effective inventory on the seven categories defined by the DOAS standard : 1) funding, 2) legal ownership, mission and governance, 3) open science 4) editorial management, editorial quality and research integrity 5) technical service efficiency, 6) visibility, communication, marketing and impact 7) equity, diversity, inclusion, multilingualism and gender equity	As many of these resources will also be relevant for ISPSs this will be a collaboration with Juliana. Many of these resources have already been surveyed for the European Diamond Capacity Hub and therefore we will align with them prior to expansion.
Editor sessions	Q2-Q4 Substitute	Organize editors’ sessions to facilitate the exchange of information specifically for editors. E.g. formats: coffee sessions/ ComiCon panel/ workshop/training/ networking events.	Examples of topics based on openjournal.nl data: technical support, funding, sourcing articles, marketing, findability, finding reviewers.

*Q1 =Jan-March, Q2=Apr-June, Q3=Jul-Sep, Q4=Oct-Dec

2. Agenda aimed at researchers

The aim of the expertise centre is to bring awareness about the changing publishing landscape and the efforts towards equitable and inclusive publishing.

Short description	Timeline	*Lead	Goal	Comments
Content for openaccess.nl	Q1-Q4	Maria	Launch the expertise centre on openaccess.nl and update website as necessary.	Bregt will need to showcase/develop content for the Researchers subpage.
Write relevant content for the target group on social media (LinkedIn)	Q1-Q4	Juliana (Bregt)	Have a consistent presence on LinkedIn. Bregt will provide at least one relevant post for researchers per month.	Develop a schedule and workflow for posts. E.g. Highlighting the ambassadors.
Newsletter to be sent to the members of the Expertise Centre	Q1-Q4	Femke (Maria)	Newsletter x 4 times/ year (each lead should have a piece for every quarter)	Bregt will need to provide at least one content piece relevant to researchers.
Showcase resources relevant for researchers on openaccess.nl	Q1	Maria (all)	Gather literature on Diamond OA publishing to present on the webpage of the expertise centre	E.g. Bring information on Diamond OA and where to find journals (e.g. Diamond Discovery Hub)
Find Diamond OA advocates (ambassadors) in 1) Social Sciences, 2) Physical Sciences, 3) Health Sciences and 4) Life Sciences	Q1	Bregt	To increase visibility amongst researchers we will engage a group of advocates/researchers to promote Diamond OA in their fields.	Decide together with ambassadors how much time commitment they have and how to proceed (brainstorm session/think thank). Encourage or support Collective actions in Science Diamond in various fields. OSC NL community
Produce content activities with advocates	Q2, Q3 and Q4	Bregt	To get information from the advocates and to distribute this information amongst researchers.	E.g. Interview/podcast with advocates who explain their experiences with, and ideas on Diamond OA publishing
Ensure Diamond OA in part of the Recognition and Rewards	Q2, Q3	Bregt	Give credit and recognition to researchers to publish/review for Diamond OA by integrating it into university recognition and rewards strategies.	Aimed at researchers and institutions on how to implement Diamond OA in university policies. Presentation at the Recognition & Rewards festival about systematically integrating Diamond OA in our R&R policies.
Showcase Diamond Open Access journals list (including NL) on the website	Q3	Maria Chiara	Increase visibility of Diamond OA journals.	Dutch journals can then be showcased and highlighted periodically on the website.
Diamond OA visible in the Journal Browser	Q4	Maria Chiara	To make researchers familiar with the existence of Diamond OA	If we want researchers to publish in, and review for Diamond OA journals we need to make them visible and easier to find. Making them visible in the Journal Browser would be very helpful for this.

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3. Agenda aimed at Institutional Publishers and Service Providers (IPSPs)

Our aim is to facilitate connections among Diamond OA publishers and institutional publishers to share expertise and best practices.

Short description	Timeline *	Lead	Goal	Comments
Content for openaccess.nl	Q1-Q4	Maria	Launch the expertise centre on openaccess.nl and update website as necessary.	Juliana will need to showcase/develop content for the IPSPs subpage.
Write relevant content for the target group on social media (LinkedIn)	Q1-Q4	Juliana (Bregt)	Have a consistent presence on LinkedIn. Newsletter x 4 times/ year (each lead should have a piece for every quarter)	Develop a schedule and workflow for posts. Juliana will provide at least one relevant post for journal editors per month.
IPSPs inventory (resource)	Q1	Juliana	Offer an overview of the IPSPs in NL, what they publish and their requirements for publishing.	Use various available lists and manual checks for a complete. Once these have been defined and characterized, they will be displayed on openaccess.nl.
Showcase existing resources for IPSPs to openaccess.nl	Q1	Juliana	Offer support to NL IPSPs	This will be a joint effort with Femke and alignment with European Diamond Capacity Hub.
Two-tiered activity: map current IPSPs standards based on DOAS standards; host online sessions with IPSPs to learn about their needs/areas of improvement based on DOAS checklist	Q2	Juliana	Understand the areas of improvement for NL-IPSPs.	Ask IPSPs to use the DOAS self-assessment tool developed by DIAMAS (this can be an interactive/guided session) and possibly the sustainability assessment. Have a follow-up session where IPSPs share their findings. Create minimum standards for NL IPSPs in collaboration with Susanne van Rijn's project
Organize one or two discussion forum format meeting(s) for one or two topics where IPSPs can discuss collaboratively how to tackle issues and work together in finding solutions (meeting)	Q3	Juliana	Support IPSPs with their needs/areas of improvement; help IPSPs professionalize their services	The meeting(s) will allow for knowledge exchange between IPSPs
Organize online meetings on the topics of the IPSP areas of improvement (meeting/training)	Q3-Q4	Juliana	Support IPSPs with their needs/areas of improvement; help IPSPs professionalize their services	Based on identified weakness areas, find experts who can do a talk to help IPSPs improve an identified service/area. Example metadata, XML, DOAB and DOAJ indexation, European accessibility act etc.

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4. Agenda for university research libraries and librarians

Our aim is to empower librarians to promote Diamond OA (e.g. by directly raising awareness within the university or by putting funds towards diamond structures, supporting Diamond initiatives etc.)

Short description	Timeline *	Lead	Goal/SMART	Comments
Content for openaccess.nl	Q1-Q4	Maria	Launch the expertise centre on openaccess.nl and update website as necessary.	Maria will need to showcase/develop content also for the librarian's subpage.
Write relevant content for the target group on social media (LinkedIn)	Q1-Q4	Juliana (Bregt)	Have a consistent presence on LinkedIn. Newsletter x 4 times/year (each lead should have a piece for every quarter)	Maria will provide at least one relevant post for librarians per month.
Showcase resources relevant for the target group on openaccess.nl	Q1	Maria (all)	Ideally at least one resource per target group should be posted.	This will be a work in progress as we are going to create new resources.
Advocacy kit on why to support Diamond OA (journals + books)	Q1	Maria	One toolkit (A4 PDF, ppt slide) that briefly explains the benefits of Diamond OA aimed at librarians. It can be expanded to other target groups.	https://www.sup.ac.uk/advocacy-toolkit
Finalize Diamond OA digital collection	Q1	Maria	We are missing 3-4 pieces to finalize the blog post. Make the collection in a pdf-format	Current status: https://www.openscience.nl/en/open-access-week-2024
Develop a national Diamond "discovery" kit that can be adapted by each librarian according to their researcher's needs.	Q2-Q4	Maria	Organize an event in which the "discovery" kit is co-created. The kit will be finalized and distributed to each university which can then be tailored to the specific needs of a department/faculty/university.	We have submitted to the openscience.nl meetings call to be able to organize this event.
Overview of Diamond Open Access publications per university	Q3	Maria/Chiara	This overview for libraries to understand which Diamond OA outlets their researchers are using.	Overview provided by the Mapping and Monitoring group of the program. It will be combined with the recommendations (see below).
Recommendations on Diamond OA support	Q4	Maria	This recommendations toolkit will contain possible routes of Diamond OA support and how to achieve this. 1) Librarians use this kit to build a case for the library to support Diamond OA 2) This can become a recommendation towards UNL policy (e.g. Taverne)	It will contain specific examples from within NL and of international universities. Propose to the WGOA to make it as a subgroup that can then be sent to UNL (e.g. Taverne). Not only financial support but also non-financial (campaign, catalogue, news, events etc.)

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5. Agenda for policy advisors

Our aim is to help policy advisors to include Diamond OA in the Recognition and Rewards program.

Short description	Timeline *	Lead	Goal/SMART	Comments
Recommendations on how to incorporate Diamond Open Access into the Recognition & Rewards program.	Q1-Q4	t.b.d.	For example, a Tips & Tricks on how to implement Diamond OA in the R&R program.	First, we need to engage with someone from R&R to determine if this would be useful.

Q1 =Jan-March, Q2=Apr-June, Q3=Jul-Sep, Q4=Oct-Dec; t.b.d.=to be determined

6. Agenda for funders

Our aim is to engage with funder bodies to persuade them to financially support Diamond OA.

Short description	Timeline *	Lead	Goal/SMART	Comments
Business case on why to support Diamond Open Access	Q1-Q4	t.b.d.	Develop a business case for the Dutch publication landscape on why to financially support Diamond OA.	First, we need to informally check if this route would be appropriate/effective. https://www.voxweb.nl/nieuws/bezuinigen-op-wetenschap-begin-met-een-open-access-revolutie

Q1 =Jan-March, Q2=Apr-June, Q3=Jul-Sep, Q4=Oct-Dec ; t.b.d.=to be determined

Appendix 1. Overview of project wide activities.

Short description	Timeline *	Lead	Goal/SMART
Updating communication plan	Q1	Maria	Incorporate the LinkedIn and Newsletter strategy and goals in the communications plan.
Updating budget	Q1-Q4	Maria	The budget is updated every time we provide an update to the steering committee which is quarterly.
Updating Program steering committee	Q1-Q4	Maria	This is done quarterly.
Updating Program sounding board	Q1-Q4	Maria	This is done quarterly.
Present and promote project at conferences or other relevant events sessions.	Q4	Maria	Present at OS festival.
Evaluation of 2025	Q4	Maria	We will evaluate our performance of year 2025 to improve the planning and agenda of 2025.
Agenda planning for 2026	Q4	Maria	We will develop the agenda for the last year of the project 2026.